

Structural characterisation of the natively unfolded enterocin EJ97

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Bacteriocins belong to the wide variety of antimicrobial ribosomal peptides synthesised by bacteria. Enterococci are Gram-positive, catalase-negative bacteria that produce lactic acid as the major end product of glucose fermentation. Many enterococcal strains produce bacteriocins, named enterocins. We describe in this work, the structural characterisation of the 44 residues-long enterocin EJ97, produced by *Enterococcus faecalis* EJ97. To this end, we have used a combined theoretical and experimental approach. First, we have characterised experimentally the conformational properties of EJ97 in solution under different conditions by using a number of spectroscopic techniques, namely fluorescence, CD, FTIR and NMR. Then, we have used several bioinformatic tools as an aid to complement the experimental information about the conformational properties of EJ97. We have shown that EJ97 is monomeric in aqueous solution and that it appears to be chiefly unfolded, save some flickering helical- or turn-like structures, probably stabilised by hydrophobic clustering. Accordingly, EJ97 does not show a cooperative sigmoidal transition when heated or upon addition of GdmCl. These conformational features are essentially pH-independent, as shown by NMR assignments at pHs 5.9 and 7.0. The computational results were puzzling, since some algorithms revealed the natively unfolded character of EJ97 (FoldIndex, the mean scaled hydrophathy), whereas some others suggested the presence of ordered structure in its central region (PONDR, RONN and IUPRED). A future challenge is to produce much more experimental results to aid the development of accurate software tools for predicting disorder in proteins.

Keywords: bacteriocin/fluorescence/FTIR/natively unfolded/NMR

Introduction

Resistance of bacterial pathogens to the different antibiotics used to treat infectious disease is now becoming endemic worldwide (Levy and Marshall, 2004). As a consequence, strong efforts are being made to develop antimicrobial compounds with novel mechanisms of action. The microbial antagonism mediated by peptides has gained considerable attention in recent years in view of their rapid bactericidal activity over a broad spectrum and the low propensity of bacteria for developing resistance against them. Antimicrobial peptides are lethal weapons used by all organisms to ward off competitors or to provide a first-line defence against infection; their antimicrobial activity is related to their ability to permeate the cytoplasmic membranes. These peptides may also have antiviral, antiparasitic and antineoplastic activities. They are classified as either non-ribosomally synthesised peptides (such as gramicidin or vancomycin, which are assembled by peptide synthetases) or ribosomally synthesised peptides (as the bacteriocins secreted by both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria). The best studied microbial group is that of lactic acid bacteria, which produce a large variety of bacteriocins active against closely related species, including food-borne virulent pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes* (Giraffa, 1995). Owing to their relatively broad inhibitory activity and to their lack of toxicity to human eukaryotic cells, bacteriocins are used in food preservation and in human therapeutics against some infections (Cotter *et al.*, 2005; Lawton *et al.*, 2007; Nes *et al.*, 2007). The use of bacteriocins in food preservation may decrease the application of potentially carcinogenic pesticides and lead to the removal of food-heat treatments, which can reduce nutritional properties. Moreover, the use of bacteriocins as therapeutics is a convenient alternative to conventional antibiotics, which are ineffective against resistant bacterial strains. For instance, the *in vivo* use of pediocin-producing bacteria has reduced the colonisation of the gastrointestinal tract by vancomycin-resistant enterococci (Millette *et al.*, 2008). In addition, bacteriocins play key roles in signal regulation, virulence and bacteria sporulation. However, the high variability among their sequences and also in their tertiary structure, as seen in the available examples, makes it difficult to predict their *in vivo* activity and makes the design of functional synthetic mimics challenging. Therefore, the complete elucidation of the primary and tertiary structures of bacteriocins appears to be of central relevance to obtain insights into the structure–function relationships and enable the design of more efficient antibiotic variants.

Bacteriocins are typically cationic peptides, with at least half of the residues being hydrophobic. As mentioned, their antimicrobial activity is related to their ability to permeate the cytoplasmic membranes of their bacterial targets. Briefly, the peptide binds to the cell anionic surface, then the peptide changes its conformation, and a concomitant aggregation of several monomer peptides leads either to the formation of a

pore in the bacterial cell wall or a carpet-like peptide cluster on top of it, which disrupts the cell membrane. Owing to this mode of action, most of the 3D structures of bacteriocins have been reported in the presence of organic solvents (TFE, DMSO or methanol) in an attempt to mimic the membrane environment (Wang *et al.*, 1999), and high-resolution structures in aqueous solution have been reported only for the circular Carnocyclin A and AS-48 (González *et al.*, 2000; Sánchez-Barrena *et al.*, 2003; Martin-Visscher *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, there are no structural pH-dependent studies for any bacteriocin in aqueous solution, although the crystals of AS-48 were grown at several pHs (Sánchez-Barrena *et al.*, 2003). The latter is relevant, since it has been suggested by Ptitsyn and coworkers that: (i) a moderately low pH could mimic the environment of a protein in the proximity of a negatively charged membrane; and (ii) the structural states acquired by the polypeptide chain at mildly acidic pHs may be similar to those populated in the proximity of a negatively charged membrane (Bychkova *et al.*, 1992, 1996; Ptitsyn *et al.*, 1993).

The enterococci are Gram-positive lactic acid bacteria, found in the gastrointestinal tract and in certain natural foods (Giraffa *et al.*, 1994; Ryser *et al.*, 1994) and fermented ones (Franz *et al.*, 1995). These bacteria also produce several bacteriocins, although the activities and structures of only a few have been studied in detail (Gálvez *et al.*, 1998; Franz *et al.*, 2007). Some time ago, we isolated from municipal wastewater, a faecal enterococcal strain EJ97 (identified as *Enterococcus faecalis*; Gálvez *et al.*, 1998), which produces enterocin EJ97 (EJ97). This enterocin is synthesised without a leader peptide and has a broad range of activity against Gram-positive bacteria including other enterococci, several species of *Bacillus*, *Listeria* as well as strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gálvez *et al.*, 1998).

We thought of interest to analyse the conformational properties of EJ97, and to that end, we have used a combined experimental (fluorescence, CD, FTIR and NMR spectroscopies) and bioinformatic approach. All spectroscopic probes indicate that EJ97 is a monomeric, natively unfolded protein in aqueous solution over a wide pH range (pH 2.0–12.0), albeit with some flickering, non-stable, helical- or turn-like conformations in some regions of the polypeptide chain. In agreement with these results, thermal and chemical denaturations do not show sigmoidal cooperative transitions. The addition of alcohols (TFE or methanol) or other polar aprotic solvents (DMSO or acetonitrile) induced aggregation, as deduced from signal broadening in the NMR spectra, without a concomitant dispersion of the amide proton signals. The application of several bioinformatics prediction programs (PredictProtein, PONDR, RONN, IUPRED and FoldIndex) provided conflicting results, since for some algorithms EJ97 is totally unfolded, whereas for others there are indications of residual conformations in the central region, where flickering helical- or turn-like structures were inferred by NMR. Thus, much more experimental work is needed to help computational biochemists to provide software tools with a more effective predicting power for disordered states.

Materials and methods

Materials

Ultra-pure urea and GdmCl were purchased from ICN Biochemicals (USA). Exact concentrations of GdmCl were

calculated from the refractive index of the solution (Pace, 1986). Deuterated methanol, DMSO, TFE, glycerol, dodecylphosphocholine (DPC) and acetonitrile were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). Standard suppliers were used for all other chemicals. Water was deionised and purified on a Millipore system.

Enterocin EJ97, produced by an *E. faecalis* strain isolated from untreated municipal waste water, was purified by a two-step procedure to a semi-preparative scale with a yield of 59.46% (Gálvez *et al.*, 1998). Bacteriocin concentration was determined from the amino acid sequence (Gill and von Hippel, 1989) by using a Shimadzu 1560 spectrophotometer (Japan). The sequence of EJ97 is (Sánchez-Hidalgo *et al.*, 2003): MLAKIKAMIKKFPNPYTLAAKLTTYEINWYKQQ YGRYPWERPVA.

Fluorescence

Fluorescence spectra were collected on a Cary Eclipse spectrofluorometer (Varian, USA) interfaced with a Peltier temperature-controlling system. Sample concentration was in the range of 1–2 μ M and the final concentration of the buffer was 10 mM. A 1-cm-pathlength quartz cell (Hellma) was used. Experiments were acquired at 298 K.

Steady-state intrinsic fluorescence measurements. Samples of EJ97 were excited at 280 and 295 nm in the pH range 2.0–12.0 to characterise possible differences in the emission of tryptophan or tyrosine residues (Pace and Scholtz, 1997). No differences, except in the spectral intensity, were observed either in the band shape or in the maximum wavelength, and then, excitation at 280 nm was used in these experiments. The slit width was set to 5 nm for the excitation and emission lights. The spectra were recorded between 300 and 400 nm. The signal was averaged for 1 s and the wavelength increment was 1 nm. Blank corrections were made in all spectra.

Salts and acids used in buffer preparation were: pH 2.0–3.0, phosphoric acid; pH 3.0–4.0, formic acid; pH 4.0–5.5, acetic acid; pH 6.0–7.0, NaH_2PO_4 ; pH 7.5–9.0, Tris acid; pH 9.5–11.0, Na_2CO_3 ; pH 11.5–13.0, Na_3PO_4 . pHs were measured with an ultra-thin Aldrich electrode in a Radiometer (Copenhagen) pH-meter. Experiments in the presence of GdmCl were carried out with the same set of parameters. Samples were prepared by taking the corresponding amount from a 7 M stock solution of GdmCl.

Changes with pH or denaturant concentration were followed by variations in the fluorescence intensity at a particular wavelength and/or in the average energy, which is defined as (Royer, 1995):

$$\langle \lambda \rangle = \frac{\sum_1^n (I_i / \lambda_i)}{\sum_1^n I_i} \quad (1)$$

Quenching experiments. Quenching of intrinsic tryptophan and tyrosine fluorescence by iodide was examined at different pHs. Excitation was at 280 and 295 nm and emission was measured from 300 to 400 nm. In the absence of GdmCl, the ionic strength was kept constant by addition of KCl. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ was added to a final concentration of 0.1 M to avoid formation of I_3^- . The slit width was set at 5 nm for both excitation and emission. The data were fitted to

(Lakowicz, 1999):

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{sv}[X], \quad (2)$$

where K_{sv} is the Stern–Volmer constant for collisional quenching; F_0 is the fluorescence in the absence of KI; and F is the measured fluorescence at any KI concentration. The range of KI concentrations was 0–0.7 M.

The dynamic and static quenching constants for acrylamide were obtained by fitting the data from different wavelengths (in the range of 330–340 nm) to the Stern–Volmer equation, which includes an exponential term to account for static quenching (Lakowicz, 1999):

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = (1 + K_{sv}[X])e^{v[X]}, \quad (3)$$

where K_{sv} is the Stern–Volmer constant for collisional quenching and v is the static quenching constant.

Thermal denaturations. Thermal denaturations were monitored by following the changes in the fluorescence emission intensity at 315, 340 and 350 nm at several pHs, after excitation at 280 and 295 nm. Excitation and emission slits were 5 nm. The scan rate was 60 K/h, with an average time of 1 s and measurements were collected every 0.2 K.

ANS-binding. Excitation wavelength was 380 nm and emission was measured from 400 to 600 nm. Slit widths were 5 nm for excitation and emission. Stock solutions of ANS were prepared in water and diluted into the samples to yield a final 100 μ M dye concentration. Dye concentrations were determined using an extinction coefficient of 8000 $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ at 372 nm. In all cases, blank solutions were subtracted from the corresponding spectra.

Circular dichroism

Circular dichroism spectra of the domain were collected on a Jasco J810 spectropolarimeter (Japan) fitted with a thermostated cell holder and interfaced with a Neslab RTE-111 water bath. The instrument was periodically calibrated with (+) 10-camphorsulphonic acid.

Steady-state measurements. Isothermal wavelength spectra at different pHs were acquired at a scan speed of 50 nm/min with a response time of 2 s and averaged over four scans at 298 K. Far-UV measurements were performed on 10 μ M solutions of EJ97 in 10 mM buffer, using 0.1 cm-pathlength quartz cells (Hellma). Experiments for testing aggregation were acquired at EJ97 concentrations of 42 and 84 μ M. Near-UV spectra were acquired using 30–40 μ M protein in a 0.5 cm-pathlength cell. All spectra were corrected by subtracting the proper baseline. The molar ellipticity, $[\Theta]$, was calculated according to:

$$[\Theta] = \frac{\Theta}{(10lcN)}, \quad (4)$$

where Θ is the measured ellipticity, l is the pathlength cell, c is the protein concentration and N is the number of amino acids (44 for EJ97).

The helical content of EJ97 was first approximated from Θ_{222} , the molar ellipticity at 222 nm, according to (Muro-Pastor *et al.*, 2003):

$$f_h = \frac{[\Theta]_{222}}{[\Theta]_{222}^{\infty}} \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right), \quad (5)$$

where f_h is the helical fraction of the protein, $[\Theta]_{222}^{\infty}$ is the mean ellipticity for an infinite α -helix at 222 nm ($-34\,500 \text{ deg cm}^2/\text{dmol}$), k is a wavelength-dependent constant (2.57 at 222 nm) and n is the number of peptide bonds. To estimate the helical content, we also deconvoluted the far-UV CD spectrum of EJ97 at pH 7.0 by using the DICHROWEB website (Whitmore and Wallace, 2004, 2008).

In the GdmCl-denaturations, the far-UV spectra were corrected by subtracting the corresponding baseline. Every chemical denaturation was repeated at least three times with new samples. The chemical denaturations were fully reversible, as shown by the curves obtained by starting from diluted 7 M GdmCl samples at physiological pH (data not shown).

In the pH-induced unfolding experiments, the pH was measured after completion of the experiments and essentially no differences were observed with the pHs calculated from the buffer stock solutions. The pH range explored was 2.0–12.0. The proper blank solutions were subtracted in all cases. The same buffers used in fluorescence were used here, and their concentration was 10 mM.

Thermal denaturations. Thermal denaturations were performed at a constant heating rate of 60 K/h and a response time of 8 s. Thermal scans were collected in the far-UV region by following the ellipticity at 222 nm from 298 to 363 K in 0.1 cm-pathlength quartz cells (Hellma) with a total protein concentration of 10 μ M. The reversibility of thermal transitions was tested by recording a new scan after cooling down to 298 K the thermally denatured samples and comparing the spectrum with that obtained before heating. In all cases, both spectra were identical (data not shown). The samples were transparent and no precipitation was observed after the reheating. The possibility of drifting of the CD spectropolarimeter was tested by running two samples containing only buffer, before and after the thermal experiments. No difference was observed between the scans. Every thermal denaturation experiment was repeated at least twice with new samples.

NMR spectroscopy

The NMR experiments were acquired on a Bruker Avance DRX-500 spectrometer or on a Bruker AMX-600 (Bruker GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) both equipped with a triple resonance probe and z-pulse field gradients.

Sample preparation, spectra acquisition and assignments. NMR samples were prepared by dissolving the lyophilised bacteriocin in a 9:1 $H_2O:D_2O$ solution. The solution was centrifuged briefly to remove insoluble protein and then transferred to a 5-mm NMR tube. Spectra were recorded on the Bruker AMX-600 spectrometer, working at a 1H frequency of 600.13 MHz, at 283, 298 and 308 K. The pH of the samples was adjusted by addition of minute amounts of DCl and

NaOD to a final value of 5.9 or 7.0. The pH was measured at the beginning and end of the experiments using a Russell glass electrode. Values of the pH reported here represent apparent values of pH, without correction for isotope effects. TSP was used as internal chemical shift reference. Bacteriocin concentration was in the range of 1.0–1.5 mM. Assignments are given in Supplementary Table S1, at pH 5.9 and 298 K. Similar assignments were obtained at pH 7.0 (data not shown).

¹H-1D spectra under different solvent conditions were acquired using 16 K data points, averaged over 512 scans and with a spectral width of 7801.69 Hz (13 ppm). ¹H-2D spectra were acquired in the phase-sensitive mode, with a spectral width of 7801.69 Hz in both dimensions and using the time proportional phase incrementation technique (Marion and Wüthrich, 1983). Standard phase-cycling sequences were used to acquire the complete set of experiments. The double-quantum filtered COSY experiment (Rance *et al.*, 1983) was acquired with a data matrix size of 8 K × 512 (*t*₂ and *t*₁, respectively) and 1 s of recycle delay, 128 scans per *t*₁ increment, and with the residual water signal attenuated by presaturation during the relaxation delay. TOCSY and NOESY experiments were acquired with a data matrix size of 4 K × 512 (*t*₂ and *t*₁, respectively), using the MLEV17 spin-lock sequence (Bax and Davis, 1985) with 50 and 80 ms of mixing time. NOESY spectra (Jeener *et al.*, 1979) were collected with mixing times of 50 and 150 ms. Typically, 128 scans were acquired per *t*₁ increment in both experiments, with the residual water signal removed by the WATERGATE sequence (Piotto *et al.*, 1993). Data were zero-filled, resolution enhanced and base line corrected using phase shifted sine bell (DQF-COSY) or square sine-bell window functions (TOCSY and NOESY) optimised in each spectrum, and processed with the XWINNMR (Bruker GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) working on a PC computer. ¹H NMR resonances were assigned using standard sequential assignment (Wüthrich, 1986). The random-coil chemical shift values of H α protons were obtained from tabulated data in model peptides (Wüthrich, 1986) and corrected for sequence effects (Schwarzinger *et al.*, 2001). Qualitative exchange experiments were carried out by dissolving the lyophilised EJ97 in D₂O at pH 5.9 and 298 K and acquiring a NOESY experiment with a mixing time of 150 ms.

Translational diffusion measurements (DOSY-NMR experiments). Translational self-diffusion measurements were performed with the pulsed-gradient spin-echo sequence in the Avance DRX-500 magnet. The following relationship exists between the translational self-diffusion parameter, *D*, and the delays during acquisition (Czypionka *et al.*, 2007):

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = -\exp\left(D\gamma_H^2\delta^2G^2\left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{3} - \frac{\tau}{2}\right)\right), \quad (6)$$

where *I* is the measured peak intensity of a particular (or a group of) resonance(s); *I*₀ is the maximum peak intensity of the same resonance(s) at the smaller gradient strength; *D* is the translational self-diffusion constant (in cm² s⁻¹); δ is the duration (in s) of the gradient; *G* is the gradient strength (in T cm⁻¹); Δ is the time (in s) between the gradients; γ_H is the gyromagnetic constant of the proton; and τ is the recovery delay between the bipolar gradients (100 μ s). Data are

plotted as *I*/*I*₀ versus *G*² and the exponential factor of the resulting curve is $D\gamma_H^2\delta^2\left(\Delta - (\delta/3 - \tau/2)\right)$, from where *D* can be easily obtained. The duration of the gradient was varied between 2.2 and 3 ms and the time between both gradients was changed from 100 to 150 ms. The most up-field shifted methyl groups (those between 0.5 and 1 ppm) were used to measure the intensity changes.

The value of *D* at infinite dilution was obtained by measuring it at different EJ97 concentrations. The gradient strength was calibrated by using the value of *D* for the residual proton water line in a sample containing 100% D₂O in a 5-mm tube, as described (Czypionka *et al.*, 2007).

Analysis of the pH-denaturation curves

The pH-denaturation experiments were analysed by assuming that both species, protonated and deprotonated, contribute to the CD spectrum and/or to the fluorescence spectra:

$$X = \frac{(X_a + X_b 10^{(\text{pH}-\text{p}K_a)})}{(1 + 10^{(\text{pH}-\text{p}K_a)})}, \quad (7)$$

where *X* is the physical property being measured (ellipticity, average energy and/or fluorescence intensity at any particular wavelength), *X*_a is its value at low pHs (acidic form), *X*_b is its value at higher pHs (basic form) and p*K*_a is the apparent p*K* of the titrating group. The apparent p*K*_a reported was obtained from three different measurements, carried out with new samples.

Fitting by nonlinear least-squares analysis to Equation (7) was carried out by using Kaleidagraph (Abelbeck software) on a PC computer.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

For FTIR studies, the protein was lyophilised and dissolved in deuterated buffer at the desired pH in D₂O. No pH-corrections were applied for isotope effects. Samples of EJ97, at a final concentration of 125 μ M, were placed between a pair of CaF₂ windows separated by a 50- μ m thick spacer, in a Harrick demountable cell at 298 K. Spectra were acquired on a Bruker FTIR instrument equipped with a DTGS detector and thermostated with a Braun water bath. The cell container was filled with dry air.

Five-hundred scans per sample were taken, averaged, apodised with a Happ-Genzel function and Fourier transformed to give a final resolution of 2 cm⁻¹. The signal-to-noise ratio of the spectra was better than 10,000:1. Baselines were subtracted and the contributions of the side-chains were removed as described (Goormaghtigh *et al.*, 1999, 2006; Güldenhaupt *et al.*, 2008). Only in those cases where there were no distortions in the spectra, the resulting difference spectra were used for analysis. To determine the amount of secondary structure components, the Amide I band in D₂O was decomposed into its constituents by curve-fitting, using a lineshape that was a combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions. The number and position of the component bands were obtained by using jointly a previous deconvolution (with a Lorentzian bandwidth of 18 cm⁻¹ and a resolution enhancement factor of 2) and the Fourier derivative (using a power of 3 and a breakpoint of 0.3) spectra. Band decomposition of the original Amide I has been described previously (Poza-Dengra *et al.*, 2009). Briefly, for

each component of the band, four parameters are considered: band position, band height, bandwidth and band shape. Thus, in a typical Amide I band decomposition with six or seven band components, the number of parameters to fit is 24–28. The number and position of the component bands are obtained through deconvolution and derivation. Initial heights are set to 90% of those in the original spectrum for the bands in the wings and for the most intense component, and they are set to 70% for the other bands. Initial bandwidths are estimated from the Fourier derivative. The Lorentzian component of the bands is initially set at 10%. Therefore, the mathematical solution of the decomposition may not be unique, but if restrictions are imposed, then the result becomes, in practice, unique. The fitting result is then evaluated by: (i) overlapping of the reconstituted overall curve on the original spectrum; and (ii) examining the residuals obtained by subtracting the fitting from the original curve.

Bioinformatic analysis of amino acid sequence of EJ97

The sequence of EJ97 was submitted to the PONDR server (www.pondr.com) and analyses were performed using the neural network predictor VL-XT and CDF (Li *et al.*, 1999; Romero *et al.*, 2001; access to PONDR was provided by Molecular Kinetics, Indianapolis, USA; E-mail: main@molecularkinetics.com). We also used the IUPRED (Dosztanyi *et al.*, 2005a, b), RONN (Yang *et al.*, 2005) and Foldindex (Priluski *et al.*, 2005) servers to allow for a comparison. The PredictProtein server was also used for prediction of structure in EJ97 (Rost *et al.*, 2004).

Results

EJ97 is a monomeric protein

Since it has been proposed that the mechanism of action of bacteriocins implies the formation of oligomeric assemblies at cell membranes, we decided to find out whether EJ97 was monomeric in aqueous solution. We first used analytical gel filtration chromatography at different pHs. At any of the explored pHs, the enterocin EJ97 eluted at 26.9 ml, a value larger than the bed volume (19.1 ml) of a Superdex 16/60 HR column. Therefore, we decided to determine the hydrodynamic radius and its oligomerisation state from the measurements of the diffusion coefficient D by DOSY-NMR experiments (Fig. 1A). As expected, D increased linearly as the concentration was reduced (Fig. 1B). If some oligomerisation equilibria were present, we should observe two (or more) intersecting straight lines, as it has been described for other oligomeric proteins (Czypionka *et al.*, 2007). In EJ97, we observed a single straight line (Fig. 1B), with a value of D at infinite dilution of $1.408 \pm 0.007 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which yields a Stokes radius, R , of 12.2 Å (see Czypionka *et al.*, 2007 for details of calculation).

It is important to note that the radius obtained from DOSY measurements is the hydrodynamic (or Stokes) radius, which can be defined as the radius of a sphere that has the same diffusion coefficient as the protein under study. This is different to the radius of gyration (R_g), which is the root-mean-square distance of all atoms in the molecule from the centre of mass (Atkins and De Paula, 2006). The relationship between both radii is (Wilkins *et al.*, 1999): $R_g = \rho R$, where ρ is $(3/5)^{1/2}$

Fig. 1. Translational diffusion coefficients (D) of EJ97. (A) The relative intensity of the most up-field shifted peaks is shown as a function of the square of the gradient strength. The exponential factor of the plot gives the apparent D of the molecule in solution at the protein concentration used. (B) NMR diffusion coefficients of EJ97 as a function of protein concentration. The bars are fitting errors to Equation 6. The solid line is the fitting to a linear equation whose y-axis intersection yields the diffusion coefficient at infinite dilution. Conditions were 293 K, in phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 50 mM. Similar results were obtained at pH 5.9.

for spherical molecules. Accordingly, the R_g of EJ97 is 9.45 Å. The theoretical ideal value of the hydrodynamic radius for an unsolvated spherical molecule, R_t , is given by: $R_t = \sqrt[3]{3M\bar{V}/4N_{Av}\pi}$, where $\bar{V}$ is the specific volume (0.737 cm³/g for EJ97); N_{Av} is Avogadro's number; and M is the molecular weight (5322.3 kDa for EJ97). For EJ97 the above expression leads to an R_t value of 11.6 Å, which is similar to that measured experimentally (12.2 Å) and it suggests that EJ97 is a monomeric species. Experimental results on several protein models suggest that R , for a well-folded protein, is given by: $R = (4.75 \pm 1.11)N^{0.29 \pm 0.02}$ (Wilkins *et al.*, 1999), what yields a value of 14 ± 3 Å for a monomeric EJ97, in agreement, within experimental error, with that obtained empirically for EJ97. The identity of the far-UV CD spectra at two EJ97 concentrations (42 and 84 μM) further confirmed that the protein was a monomer over that concentration range (Supplementary Fig. S1), as previously deduced from DOSY experiments (Fig. 1B).

It is illustrative to compare our experimentally determined value for R_g with the theoretical values expected for a disordered polypeptide chain. We can calculate the R_g of an unfolded protein by using Flory's scaling law: $R_g = R_0 N^{\nu}$, where R_0 is a constant, and ν is a solvent-dependent scaling factor. By using the values of R_0 and ν reported by Plaxco and co-workers (Kohn *et al.*, 2004), a value of 19.99 Å is obtained for R_g in EJ97. For a freely jointed chain, the radius of gyration is (Atkins and De Paula, 2006): $\langle R_g^2 \rangle = l^2 N / 6$, where l is the link length set to 4 nm (Paz *et al.*, 2008). This equation yields a value of 108.3 Å for $\langle R_g^2 \rangle^{1/2}$ in EJ97. Taken

together, these results indicate that the monomeric EJ97 polypeptide chain is more compact than a fully disordered, or than a freely jointed, chain.

EJ97 is a natively unfolded protein

To test the structure of EJ97 in aqueous solutions, we have used a combined experimental and theoretical approach. Within the experimental part, we have employed the following spectroscopic techniques: fluorescence, FTIR, CD and NMR.

Spectroscopic measurements

Fluorescence. (1) *Steady-state fluorescence:* We recorded fluorescence spectra to map the tertiary structure of the protein around the fluorescent residues (tryptophan and tyrosine; Schmid, 1997). The EJ97 enterocin has two tryptophan residues at positions 29 and 39 and five tyrosines at positions 16, 25, 30, 34 and 37. The emission fluorescence spectrum of the bacteriocin at pH 7.0, either by excitation at 280 or 295 nm, is red-shifted, with a maximum at 343 nm (Fig. 2A, blank squares, continuous line). These results indicate that: (i) tryptophans make the larger contribution to the fluorescence spectrum; and (ii) the tryptophans (or at least one of them) are partially solvent-exposed (in an aqueous environment the fluorescence maximum should be at ca. 350 nm (Schmid, 1997)).

The pH-dependence of $\langle \lambda \rangle$ was unaltered except at basic pHs (Fig. 2B, filled squares, right axis), suggesting that the conformation of the protein was unmodified. At high pHs, however, $\langle \lambda \rangle$ increased, probably because of structural rearrangements due to the titration of basic residues or,

alternatively, to basic hydrolysis. A similar behaviour was observed at other wavelengths (315, 335 and 350 nm) (data not shown).

(2) *ANS-binding experiments:* ANS is a fluorescence probe which binds to large enough loosely packed solvent accessible hydrophobic cores (Semisotnov *et al.*, 1987). When bound, the spectrum fluorescence maxima shifts from 520 to 480 nm. It is of note that completely unfolded proteins do not bind the probe, in spite of displaying a large amount of solvent-exposed hydrophobic surface, and containing, in some cases, local hydrophobic clusters (Ptitsyn, 1995). This is due to the fact that the polypeptide patches are not close enough (and probably not large enough), in the random-coil ensemble, to promote binding. In our case, the maxima of the ANS spectra, in the presence of EJ97, were at 520 nm at all pHs explored, what indicates that the protein does not bind ANS at a large extent (data not shown).

(3) *Examination of tryptophan and tyrosine solvent-exposure by fluorescence quenching:* To further examine whether there could be some tertiary structure around the two tryptophans and/or five tyrosines at pH 7.0, which could hamper the access of solvent to the aromatic moieties, we studied iodide and acrylamide quenching, in the presence and absence of denaturants (Table I). The K_{sv} values were larger in acrylamide than in KI, as observed in other proteins (Muro-Pastor *et al.*, 2003). The K_{sv} parameters in the presence of GdmCl or at basic pHs were similar, suggesting that under those conditions the tryptophan and the tyrosine residues were fully exposed. However, at physiological and acidic pHs, the K_{sv} parameters were smaller than those at basic pH, indicating that the tryptophan and tyrosine residues

Fig. 2. Fluorescence and far-UV CD experiments of EJ97. (A) Fluorescence spectra of the bacteriocin in aqueous solution, phosphate buffer (blank squares, continuous line) and in 5 M GdmCl (filled squares, dotted line) at pH 7.0. (B) Changes in $\langle \lambda \rangle$ (right axis, filled squares) and in $[\Theta]_{222}$ (left axis, blank squares) upon pH. (C) Changes in $\langle \lambda \rangle$ (right axis, filled squares) and in $[\Theta]_{222}$ (left axis, blank squares) upon GdmCl concentration. (D) Far-UV spectra of EJ97 in aqueous solution, phosphate buffer (blank squares, continuous line) and at 5 M GdmCl, pH 7.0 (filled squares, dotted line). The conditions were 2 μ M of EJ97 for fluorescence and CD spectra, 10 μ M; the buffer concentration was 10 mM in all cases. Spectra were acquired in either 1-cm-(fluorescence) or 0.1-cm-(CD) pathlength cells. Experiments were acquired at 298 K.

Table I. Quenching parameters of EJ97 in KI and acrylamide^a

Conditions	280 nm		295 nm	
	K_{sv} (M^{-1}) (KI)	K_{sv} (M^{-1}) (acrylamide)	K_{sv} (M^{-1}) (KI)	K_{sv} (M^{-1}) (acrylamide)
pH 1.4 ^b		4.9 ± 0.8		4.1 ± 0.7
pH 7.3	0.9 ± 0.1	5.7 ± 0.4	0.72 ± 0.07	4 ± 1
pH 12.0	4.0 ± 0.1	11 ± 1	0.8 ± 0.1	7 ± 1
5 M GdmCl	4.3 ± 0.4	12 ± 1	3.6 ± 0.5	8 ± 1

^aErrors are data fit errors to Equation (2) (KI) or Equation (3) (acrylamide). The constants were obtained by fitting the fluorescence intensity at 338 nm versus concentration of quenching agent. Experiments were carried out at 298 K.

^bAt acidic pH, EJ97 precipitated in the presence of KI.

Table II. Secondary structural analysis of EJ97 (in%) as determined by CD^a and FTIR^b

Structural assignment	Circular dichroism (k2D)	FTIR
α -helix	45	0
β -Sheet	14	5.6
β -Turns or loops		35.9
Random-coil	41	58.5

^aCD experiments were acquired at pH 7.0 (phosphate buffer), at 10 μ M of protein concentration. Experiments were carried out at 298 K. Deconvolution was carried out by using the k2D software.

^bExperiments were carried out at 298 K.

though being solvent-exposed, as suggested from the fluorescence maximum wavelength, are not fully accessible.

(4) *Chemical denaturation*: The spectrum in 5 M GdmCl (or in 6 M urea, data not shown) has a smaller intensity and a red-shift larger than that observed in the absence of denaturant (Fig. 2A, filled squares, dotted line). A linear behaviour was observed for $\langle \lambda \rangle$ (Fig. 2C, filled squares, right axis) up to ~ 3 M GdmCl, in agreement with the tendency expected for solvent-exposed aromatic rings (Schmid, 1997). At higher concentrations, a steeper decrease in $\langle \lambda \rangle$ was observed. Similar results were obtained when intensity was monitored at other wavelengths (data not shown).

Circular dichroism experiments. (1) *Far-UV CD*: Far-UV CD was used as a spectroscopic probe sensitive to protein secondary structure (Woody, 1995; Kelly and Price, 2000). The CD spectrum of EJ97 at pH 7.0 showed a minimum negative ellipticity at ca. 208 nm, and a broad shoulder at 230 nm (Fig. 2D, blank squares, continuous line), which can be attributed to the presence of helical- or turn-like conformations, or alternatively, to aromatic residues (Vuilleumier *et al.*, 1993; Woody, 1995; Kelly and Price, 2000). The estimated population of α -helix- or turn-like structures from Equation (5) is 21% ($[\Theta]_{222}$ is -7917.17 deg cm^2 dmol). Deconvolution by using the k2D algorithm leads to the results shown in Table II.

$[\Theta]_{222}$ shows a gradual increase (in absolute value) at increasing pHs (Fig. 2B, blank squares, left axis). At acidic pHs there is a steep decrease in its value, which can be

ascribed to a titration whose pK_a cannot be determined with precision due to the absence of baseline in the acidic region; this titration must be associated with an aspartic or glutamic residue (Thurkill *et al.*, 2006). The gradual increase (in absolute value) of the ellipticity at basic pHs parallels that observed in fluorescence and suggests an increase in helical- or turn-like structures (Kelly and Price, 2000).

(2) *Chemical denaturation*: $[\Theta]_{222}$ decreased (in absolute value) gradually as the concentration of GdmCl was raised above 3 M (Fig. 2C, blank squares, left axis), indicating that the denaturation was a non-cooperative process. This result supports the existence, under native conditions, of some residual structure in EJ97, which does not unfold cooperatively. Whether that structure is local or involves short-lived long-range interactions cannot be determined.

(3) *Near-UV*: We used near-UV CD to detect possible changes in the asymmetric environment of aromatic residues (Woody, 1995; Kelly and Price, 2000). The near-UV of EJ97 was very weak with no intense bands (data not shown). The lack of a near-UV signal is indicative of the absence of an asymmetric environment for the quite abundant aromatic residues (2 Trp, 5 Tyr and 1 Phe) present in the bacteriocin.

(4) *Thermal denaturations*: To further investigate the possible presence of residual secondary structure in EJ97, as suggested by the above results, we carried out thermal denaturations following the changes in ellipticity at 222 nm. The ellipticity did not change in a sigmoidal fashion, but it showed a linear behaviour at every explored pH (Supplementary Fig. S2A). This result indicates an absence of cooperativity, as expected for a non-compact structure and agrees with the behaviour observed in the thermal denaturation followed by fluorescence (Supplementary Fig. S2B) and the chemical denaturation monitored by CD (Fig. 2C).

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

FTIR is a powerful method to investigate protein secondary structure. The main advantage in comparison with CD and fluorescence is that FTIR is much more sensitive to the presence of β -structure or random-coil. In proteins, structural information is obtained by analysing the Amide I region of the spectrum (1700–1600 cm^{-1}). The absorbance of this band is mainly due to the stretching vibration of the carbonyl peptide bond, whose frequency is highly sensitive to hydrogen bonding and thus to protein secondary structure (Surewicz and Mantsch, 1988). The deconvoluted Amide I of the FTIR spectrum of EJ97 shows intense bands at 1673 and 1646 cm^{-1} ; the first band corresponds to the presence of β -turns and the second to disordered populations. The blind application of the methods described in the Materials and Methods section yields a high percentage (94%) of β -turns and random-coil conformations (Table II), at difference with the results obtained by CD (see above).

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

Our initial objective was to solve the structure of EJ97 in aqueous solution. The spectrum of the bacteriocin in aqueous solution appears well-dispersed both in the methyl (Supplementary Fig. S3, bottom) and in the amide regions (Fig. 3, bottom). A summary of the observed inter-residue sequential NOEs is shown in Fig. 4. Continuous sequential backbone–backbone NOEs facilitated the assignment of the

majority of the backbone resonances, except for the segments Met1-Leu2-Ala3, (in the N-terminal region) Gln32-Gln33-Tyr34, and Pro42-Val43-Ala44, (in the C terminus of the

Fig. 3. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of EJ97 under several conditions. Amide region of EJ97 at pH 5.9 in H_2O (bottom), 50% DMSO (middle) (a similar spectrum was obtained in the presence of 50% acetonitrile, data not shown), 50% TFE (top) (a similar spectrum was obtained in the presence of 50% methanol, data not shown). Protein concentration was 1 mM in acetate buffer concentration (20 mM); experiments were carried out at 298 K.

protein), where some backbone proton resonances have been left unassigned (Supplementary Table S1).

The majority of the prolines (Pro13, Pro15 and Pro42) were in a *trans* conformation, as judged by the intense NOEs observed between their $\text{H}\delta$'s resonances and those of the $\text{H}\alpha$'s of the preceding residue (Phe12, Asn14 and Arg41, respectively). The $\text{H}\alpha$ proton of Tyr37 is the only one which did not show intense $\alpha\delta(i, i + 1)$ NOEs with the following proline. Also, Tyr37, Pro38 and Trp39 did show two set of signals (Supplementary Table S1) for all their protons. We suggest that the *cis* conformation around the proline peptidic angle may be favoured in this case, due to the bulky side-chains of the two aromatic residues, increasing consequently the intensities of the signals corresponding to that isomer. This can also be easily observed in Fig. 3 (bottom) where instead of the expected two indole signals for the two tryptophan residues, three resonances show up. This question made the assignment of backbone resonances at the C-terminal region of EJ97 especially difficult.

The enterocin EJ97 has a large number of aromatic residues: 1 Phe, 2 Trp and 5 Tyr, which normally are easily identified in the NMR spectra due to the intense NOEs of the aromatic residues with their own $\text{H}\beta$ s and NH protons. The assigned aromatic protons did not show contacts with any other proton belonging to an amino acid more than three-residues apart.

In the segment spanning residues Thr17 to Tyr30, we could observe sequential $\text{NN}(i, i + 1)$ contacts, but no long-range NOEs (far beyond three residues from the corresponding amino acid) could be detected. However, most of the $\text{H}\alpha$ protons in the peptide showed negative conformational shifts (Fig. 4 and Supplementary Table S1), suggesting the presence of segmental 'nascent-helices'.

In the hydrogen/deuterium exchange experiments all amide protons disappeared at pH 5.9 within 20 min (Supplementary Fig. S5), which indicates that no amide proton is hydrogen-bonded.

Finally, it is of note that the chemical shifts of the methyl proton in a few residues, such as Ala19 which appears at 0.62 ppm (Supplementary Table S1), are strongly up-field shifted. Although there is no evidence of stable tertiary structure, as shown by: (i) the lack of cooperativity in the thermal and chemical denaturation experiments; and (ii) the hydrogen-exchange behaviour, the presence of those up-field shifted methyl protons suggests the existence of hydrophobic clusters drawn by local interactions between the side-chains of the well abundant aromatic residues, as described for other peptides and protein fragments (de Prat Gay, 1996a, b).

Fig. 4. Summary of NMR data. NOEs are classified as strong, medium or weak, according to the height of the bar underneath the sequence. The corresponding sequential $\text{H}\alpha$ NOE with the $\text{H}\delta$ s of the adjacent proline residue are indicated by an open rectangle in the bar corresponding to the $\alpha\text{N}(i, i + 1)$ NOEs. Residues whose conformational shifts are larger than 0.1 ppm, positive or negative, are represented by a '+' or '-', respectively; '0' applies to those residues whose conformational shifts are lower (positive or negative) than 0.1 ppm; an '*' indicates residues which were not assigned. In Gly35, one $\text{H}\alpha$ proton has a negative conformational shift and the other a positive value.

Effects of putative protein structure enhancers

Since it is well-known that TFE and, in general, organic alcohols enhance the population of helical contents in peptides (Fregeau-Gallagher *et al.*, 1997; Wang *et al.*, 1999), we decided to investigate the effect of them on the conformational properties of EJ97. The presence of 50% TFE enhances very significantly the population of turn-like or α -helical residual structures as judged by the substantial increase in the absolute value of $[\Theta]_{222}$ (Supplementary Fig. S1). In the NMR spectra, the presence of alcohols (50% TFE or 50% methanol) or other polar aprotic solvents (50% acetonitrile or 50% DMSO) provokes a general signal broadening (Fig. 3, middle and top), precluding assignment of 2D-NMR spectra.

We also tested the structure of EJ97 in the presence of 1 M Na_2SO_4 , which has been shown to stabilise partially folded states in other proteins (Pedersen *et al.*, 2006). There were no differences in the CD spectrum of the Na_2SO_4 sample, when compared with that of EJ97 in aqueous solution with no salt added (Supplementary Fig. S1); further, no effects were appreciated on the NMR spectrum (Supplementary Fig. S4, top). Other osmolytes, like sucrose, trehalose or glycerol are also known to act as protein stabilising agents (Chen *et al.*, 2006). However, the CD spectra of EJ97 in the presence of glycerol did not show any significant increase in the CD signal at 220 nm (Supplementary Fig. S1); in the same way, the use of deuterated-glycerol in the ^1H -1D-NMR spectrum did not show any change in the dispersion of the amide signals (data not shown). Then, it appears that neither salt nor osmolytes do stabilise any residual structure in EJ97.

Finally, there are reports in the literature on structures of bacteriocins obtained in the presence of deuterated-DPC (Fregeau-Gallagher *et al.*, 1997; Uteng *et al.*, 2003). We then decided to explore the behaviour of EJ97 in the presence of 4.5 mM DPC (Fregeau-Gallagher *et al.*, 1997). Interestingly, the CD showed an increase in the percentage of helical structure similar to that obtained in 50% TFE (Supplementary Fig. S1). Unfortunately, DPC provoked a signal broadening in the ^1H -1D-NMR (Supplementary Fig. S4, bottom), which deteriorated the quality of the 2D spectra and precluded to pursue the assignment of the protein resonances.

To conclude, all spectroscopic results show that EJ97 is essentially unstructured, although there is evidence of some residual fluctuating helical- or turn-like structures, which are not hydrogen-bonded.

Theoretical analysis of the EJ97 sequence. The protein has a high content of alanine (11.4%), lysine (13.6%) and proline (9.1%), which are disorder-promoting residues. However, it also has a high percentage of tryptophan (4.5%) and tyrosine (11.4%), which are order-promoting residues (Fig. 5A). Interestingly enough, a similar high content of tyrosine residues has been observed in antitoxins (Cherny and Gazit, 2004), a new family of natively unfolded proteins with antibacterial functions.

Results from the application of different theoretical predictors were puzzling. The VL-XT program predicts that most of the polypeptide chain is ordered: from residues Lys10 to Gly35 (Fig. 5B). Further, the CDF (cumulative distribution function) analysis of PONDR (predictor of natural disordered

Fig. 5. *In silico* analysis of EJ97 sequence. (A) Distribution of order- and disorder-promoting amino acids in the sequence of EJ97. The distribution shows the deviation in amino acid composition of the domain from the average values in the Swiss-Prot data base (as obtained from the World Wide Web at <http://www.expasy.org/sprot/relnotes/relstat.html>). (B) PONDR predictions of unstructured regions of EJ97 sequence with the use of VL-XT predictor. The predictor score is plotted against the residue number. The threshold is 0.5 and residues with a higher score are considered disordered. (C) IUPred prediction of unstructured regions (long disorder prediction) of EJ97. The threshold is also 0.5. The two black lines in the last two panels correspond to the helical fragments predicted by the PredictProtein server.

regions) predicts that the domain is above the established limit for an ordered protein, indicating a well-folded polypeptide chain (Supplementary Fig. S6A). Results similar to those of VL-XT were obtained by using the IUPRED (Fig. 5C) and RONN (data not shown) web servers. The agreement between these three theoretical approaches is very good even though they use different calculation methods. The PredictProtein software also predicts that the regions Leu2-Lys11 and Pro15-Gln33 should be helical (black squares on top of Fig. 5B and C). Interestingly, the second predicted helical region (Pro15 to Gln33) coincides with the polypeptide patch where the largest number of $\text{NN}(i, i + 1)$ NOEs were observed (Fig. 4).

Conversely, other algorithms predict a disordered structure for EJ97. The charge-hydrophobicity phase-space analysis of PONDR indicates the unfolded nature of the domain (Supplementary Fig. S6B). Foldindex predicts that the whole

EJ97 polypeptide chain is disordered, with an unfoldability value of -0.070 , a charge of 0.098 and a phobic value of 0.423 .

Discussion

EJ97 is a natively unfolded protein with some flickering helical- or turn-like structures

Natively unfolded proteins (or intrinsically disordered proteins) are proteins with substantial regions of disordered structure under physiological conditions (Dyson and Wright, 2005; Fink, 2005; Tompa, 2002). In spite of their lack of structure, these proteins are nevertheless functional by undergoing a structural transition to a folded form by interaction with a target ligand or when set in an appropriate environment. The use of a combination of theoretical predictions and experimental methods is recommended in order to assess intrinsic disorder (Tompa, 2002).

In this work, we have shown experimentally that EJ97 lacks in aqueous solution a well-defined tertiary structure, and behaves largely as a disordered protein, with neither a stable hydrogen-bonded secondary structure nor a well-formed hydrophobic core. The absence of cooperativity during the thermal (Supplementary Fig. S2) and chemical denaturations (monitored by CD and fluorescence) (Fig. 2C) also indicate that the tertiary structure of EJ97, if any, is very weak and no stable hydrophobic core is formed. Such non-cooperative transitions are typically observed in chemical or thermal denaturations of partially folded states devoid of persistent long-range tertiary contacts (Calloni *et al.*, 2008).

However, some evidence of residual secondary structure has been found, as deduced from FTIR (Table II) and CD (Fig. 2D and Table II). The broad band at 222 nm in the far-UV CD spectra indicates the presence of helical- or turn-like secondary structures, which are further supported by: (i) CD deconvolution methods (Table II); and (ii) the calculation of helical structure by Equation (5). FTIR also indicates the existence of turn-like conformations, in a higher percentage ($\sim 36\%$) than that observed by CD (Table II). The differences between the populations of secondary structure reported by these techniques could be due to: (i) the corresponding deconvolution procedures used; (ii) the presence of aromatic residues (CD), which also absorb at 222 nm (Vuilleumier *et al.*, 1993; Woody, 1995; Kelly and Price, 2000); or (iii) the empirical character of the equation used in determining the percentage of secondary structure (CD). Whatever the exact reason of the discrepancy, we may conclude that EJ97 does show some residual secondary structure. The presence of helical- or turn-like conformations is also supported by several pieces of NMR evidence. First, the conformational shifts of the H_{α} protons of residues in EJ97 are up-field shifted (Supplementary Table S1), in keeping with that described for weakly populated helical peptides (Jiménez *et al.*, 1992). Second, some $NN(i, i + 1)$ contacts, a further indicator of nascent-helices in peptides, were detected in EJ97 (Fig. 4). And finally, the up-field shifted resonances of methyl protons of several amino acids point towards the existence of local clusters promoted by aromatic residues (de Prat Gay, 1996a, b). Moreover, the presence of helical- or turn-like conformations would explain why the experimentally determined Stokes radius of EJ97 is smaller than that

expected for a completely random-coil polymer. However, the hydrophobic interactions may not involve a large number of hydrophobic residues and, probably, they are not resistant enough to ensure binding of the ANS probe.

We have seen that the results from the application of different theoretical predictors are puzzling. Thus, whereas some algorithms predict for EJ97 a well-folded polypeptide chain, others predict a disordered structure. Furthermore, the PredictProtein software generates a disordered structure with two helical regions, one of which coincides satisfactorily with the polypeptide region where the largest number of $NN(i, i + 1)$ NOEs were experimentally observed. In view of the conflicting results obtained by the application of the several predicting algorithms, we do not lend too much credit to the results provided by the theoretical methods. Rather, the main conclusion to draw is that much more experimental results from different protein systems are needed in order to provide software tools with a more effective predicting power of disordered states.

Comparison with other bacteriocins

There are several reports on the structure of other bacteriocins, but most of them refer to studies carried out in the presence of membrane-mimicking environments such as micelles, liposomes or TFE (Fregeau-Gallagher *et al.*, 1997; Wang *et al.*, 1999; Watson *et al.*, 2001; Hsu *et al.*, 2002; Kawulka *et al.*, 2003; Uteng *et al.*, 2003; Sprules *et al.*, 2004; Haugen *et al.*, 2005; Fimland *et al.*, 2008; Rogne *et al.*, 2008). The structures of the circular AS-48 (González *et al.*, 2000; Sánchez-Barrena *et al.*, 2003) and carnocyclin (Martin-Visscher *et al.*, 2009), both belonging to Class IV, are the only ones which have been reported in aqueous solution. The 3D structures determined for members of the four classes of bacteriocins are different in agreement with their distinct features. The structures of lantibiotics (Class I) have long been thought to be compact and rigid given the lanthionine ring linkages and their relatively small size (Brötz and Sahl, 2000). Among the Class IIa bacteriocins, which are characterised by the conserved sequence YGNVXC (where X may be any of the 20 amino acid residues) at the N terminus, the structures are different due to the high residue variability in their N-terminal regions; nevertheless, their C-terminal regions appear to adopt a helical structure, which is thought to play a critical role in cell recognition. All these peptides are unstructured in water (although in some examples no evidence is shown), but they become structured when exposed to membrane-mimicking environments. Interestingly enough, we have used IUPRED, RONN and Foldindex with sakacin p (Uteng *et al.*, 2003), carnobacteriocin B2 (Wang *et al.*, 1999) and leucocin A (Fregeau-Gallagher *et al.*, 1997), belonging to Class II bacteriocins, and have obtained similar results to those found for EJ97 (Fig. 5B and C) (data not shown).

Unfortunately, the presence of alcohols (TFE or methanol) or other organic solvents (DMSO or acetonitrile) did not induce in EJ97 a helical structure stable enough to allow characterisation by 2D-NMR methods. This is similar to that observed recently in other peptide antibiotics, which show aggregation and unstructured states in the presence of alcohols (Martin *et al.*, 2004). Then, it appears that the propensity to adopt a stable helical structure (which seems to be the preferred conformation according to the theoretical

prediction studies) depends strongly on the environment. Thus, as a first approach we decided to study the conformational preferences of EJ97 in the presence of other potential stabilising agents such as osmolytes, Na₂SO₄ and DPC. According to the CD spectra, DPC and TFE enhance significantly the residual helical content, what is an important result in our view. Unfortunately, the signal broadening in the 2D-NMR spectra did not allow to analyse further that behaviour. Conversely, osmolytes (such as glycerol) or salts (such as Na₂SO₄) have no effect on the residual helical structure. Then, we conclude that the presence of a more hydrophobic environment (such as that provided by TFE or DPC) increases the existing residual helical populations but not to the point of entirely stabilise them.

As a second approach, we decided to study the conformational preferences of EJ97 as a function of pH, since it has been suggested that an acidic environment could mimic the membrane surroundings (Bychkova *et al.*, 1992, 1996; Ptitsyn *et al.*, 1993). Our results obtained by fluorescence and NMR (at two different pHs) show that the structure of EJ97 remains unaltered in a wide pH range, and that it does not adopt a molten globule conformation, as judged by the absence of ANS-binding. However, we observed pH-dependent changes in the far-UV CD spectra, which may be a result of conformational variations around the aromatic residues, since no changes were shown in the NMR spectra at pH 5.9 and 7.0. Alternatively, these changes might be due to alterations in the residual secondary structure not detected by NMR because of line broadening. Thus, considering the changes occurring at basic pHs, as observed in the fluorescence and CD spectra (Fig. 2B), it is tempting to suggest that at those high pHs the enterocin might adopt a highly helical conformation. Probably, the protonation of some particular residues might hamper the acquisition of a helical structure at low or neutral pHs even in the presence of highly hydrophobic alcohols.

Supplementary data

Supplementary data are available at *PEDS* online.

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